

TITLE:

The Role of Audio-Based Repeated Reading in Improving EFL Learners' Reading Comprehension at Vo Minh Duc High School

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Binh Duong 2022

STATEMENT OF AUTHORSHIP

Title of paper: **THE ROLE OF AUDIO-BASED REPEATED READING IN IMPROVING EFL LEARNERS' READING COMPREHENSION AT VO MINH DUC HIGH SCHOOL**

I hereby confirm that I am the sole author of the paper presented.

Where the work of others has been consulted, this is duly acknowledged in the paper's bibliography. I have also not consulted any other unnamed onlinesources. All verbatim or referential use of the sources named in the bibliography has been specifically indicated in the text.

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Signature

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ABSTRACT

Silent reading as well as reading comprehension was very important for EFL learners. According to a study of Shimono T. R. (2018), his study indicates that students' rate gains were high, it was from 13 to 17 words every minute. However, learners may not understand the meaning of words in some specific contexts within silent reading. Laberge and Samuels (1974) show that many students realize reading difficult in understanding the semantic units of phrases or sentences in texts relating to the low-level reading process as well as semantic sides. Hence, the issue leading to this work is to help EFL learners improve reading comprehension. The goal of this study is to see how audio-based RR affects students' comprehension levels in 10th grade. Also, this paper focuses on exploring the pros and cons of audio-based RR to fulfill the given gap. It helps learners understand more obviously and be easy to concentrate on reading. A pretest and posttest, a semi opened-ended interview, and a Likert-scale questionnaire were used to gather data. The study was done with quantitative research method and they were gathered before and after a total intervention of 12 weeks, twice a week on Wednesday and Sunday afternoons for 45 minutes each time. The participants were a mix of tenth-grade basic education students, with the majority struggling with classroom reading activities, as evidenced by grades, attitudes toward reading tasks, and standardized test score results. In Thu Dau Mot, the setting was a Vo Minh Duc public high school. The data was examined by the teacher-researcher, discovered that the treatment increased the study group's reading comprehension into reading tasks and activities.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Meaning
RR	Repeated Reading
EFL	English as a Foreign Language
L1	First language
L2	Second language
SPSS	The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
Sta.	Statement (e.g. Sta.1 = Statement 1)
Q	Question (e.g. Q1 = Question 1)

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CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter includes five main parts with the first section called background to the study providing a preliminary review of the existing literature on the area of my research, also this part will present gaps leading to the research of the topic. The second part is to identify the aim of the study. The fourth part is to show specific research questions. Following this, stating the contributions of the research is the significance of the study part. Last but not least, thesis outline part with the purpose presents a detailed description of the major parts in the study.

1.1. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The primary goal of reading is to grasp the contents of the book; nevertheless, many students still struggle to do so, despite receiving extensive instruction in their reading classes. As a result, this problem has become the largest limitation for EFL students in history. That is because the EFL students there discovered that reading in English is quite different from reading in their native tongue, so they have always had to deal with some complex issues, such as the many linguistic characteristics, lexical, and syntactic parts of the English text they have read. Students who are learning English as a second language have a lot of difficulty reading and comprehending English materials. Furthermore, learners' lack of enthusiasm for reading has harmed their reading comprehension abilities. In teaching grade 10 students at Vo Minh Duc high school, it seems that many students find reading difficult to understand the meaning of words, phrases or sentences in reading texts which is directly related to the low-level reading process (Laberge & Samuels, 1974) or semantic aspects. Semantics is a component of reading effectiveness by understanding how a writer expresses meaning in appropriate use contexts or pragmatics. Students require new reading material to keep them interested in reading so that they can retain and grasp what they have learnt. As a result, if students are interested in what is being taught, they will be driven to learn more. After examining different useful supporting strategy, RR is a potential method for improving grade tenth students' reading comprehension.

Teaching grade 10 students at Vo Minh Duc high school, it seems that many students find reading difficult to understand the meaning of words, phrases or sentences in reading texts which is directly related to the low-level reading process (Laberge & Samuels, 1974) or semantic aspects. Semantics is a component of reading effectiveness by understanding how a writer expresses meaning in appropriate use contexts or pragmatics. After examining different useful supporting strategy, repeated reading is a potential method for improving grade tenth students.

1.2. AIMS OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to examine how repeated reading strategy with audio model affects students' ability to understand semantic units in texts and also to identify the advantageous and disadvantageous aspects of repeated reading to learners' ability to understand semantic units in texts. Some reasons for choosing this are that there must be a deep solution to tackle the current difficulties of understanding word meaning timely for grade 10 students. RR method has been used effectively with elementary and secondary learners by Begeny, Daly, & Valleley (2006), and Freeland, Skinner, Jackson, McDaniel, & Smith (2000). Therefore, this paper will be examining more on tertiary context to find out whether RR is effective or not to help Grade 10 students understand semantic units with the support of audio model. Another reason includes the illustration of the effectiveness as well as the appropriate implementation of the Repeated Reading audio model in the tertiary education context to solve the current problems in grade 10 students at Vo Minh Duc high school.

1.3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study will aim to fulfill a gap by examining the effects of RR on EFL learners by employing audio to develop the semantic understanding in Vo Minh Duc high school as well as uncover potential beneficial sides and detrimental sides of the method. To reach the aims aforementioned, two research questions need to be answered:

Research Question 1: To what extent does audio-based RR affect learners' reading comprehension?

Research Question 2: What are the upsides and downsides of audio-based RR to readers?

1.4. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study will provide the insights into the effect of audio-based repeated reading strategy on tertiary school context, especially grade 10. Through this study, the participants and also teachers will realize the importance of RR with audio to improve the reading learning routine and also to interest EFL students in reading comprehension learning. Through this study, the effectiveness of audio-based RR will be shown highly, strengthened and also proved helpful. Furthermore, the data analysis in this study will help examine more about the negative impacts of RR and also explore more advantageous aspects of RR with audio.

1.5. THESIS OUTLINE

This research is divided into six chapters. The study's background, aims, research questions, and significance are all discussed in the first chapter. This chapter discusses the study's purpose as well as the instruments utilized to collect data for the research analysis. The second part presents a theoretical foundation as well as previously published works, while the third and final chapter will concentrate on linked works. The third chapter discusses research methodology, population and sampling, data collection procedures, and data analysis methods; this is the most significant aspect of the study because it examines the therapy. Data analysis

is covered in the fourth chapter, which entails analyzing, interpreting, and presenting data in the form of tables or figures to better show results. The fifth chapter's results and conclusion section will provide the investigation's findings to see if they are comparable or different from the findings of the literature review session. The conclusion chapter provides an overview of the key results, limits, and future directions and suggestions. The following sections are made up of references and appendices.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section, literature review presents the definition of reading, repeated reading, advantages and disadvantages of repeated reading as well. Besides, previous studies are shown together with relating sections to the research.

2.1. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Silent reading, as well as reading comprehension was essential for EFL learners. According to a study by Shimono T. R. (2018), his study indicates that students' rate gains were high, it was from 13 to 17 words every minute. However, learners may not understand the meaning of words in some specific contexts within silent reading. Laberge and Samuels (1974) show that many students realize reading difficulty in understanding the semantic units of phrases or sentences in texts relating to the low-level reading process and semantic sides. Therefore, this paper will focus on the use of the audio model with Repeated Reading. It helps learners understand more obviously and be easy to concentrate on reading.

Repeated reading is assumed as the basis with the idea of the reader's fluency being improved through reading a text repetitiously. As cited in Raney and Rayner (1995), the duration of reading can be shortened when a learner is made to do reading of a text or a word for the second time. Therefore, Repeated Reading is to support the reader with the practice in context for the text. When the reader goes through the text repetitiously, the learner can become familiar with the words and sentences appearing in the text as well as structures of the text and semantic units. In Repeated Reading, the first reading plays an important role as a foundation for the readings to go, and the reader can read the text much more fluently thanks to transferring the experience of reading that the learner has accumulated during the first reading to the second reading.

2.1.1. Definition of reading comprehension

The learner's comprehension is the primary objective of reading education. Reading is essential for a student's academic performance as well as influencing his or her future life decisions. The reader must constantly decode words, grasp language in context, and adjust to the information provided directly in the text as part of this complicated cognitive process. Reading is a cognitive activity that is energetic, interesting, and complicated.

2.1.2. Repeated Reading

2.1.2.1. Definition

Numerous oral reading, or RR, entails multiple, subsequent interactions with the same visual material, with the key being repetition—whether of the same words, phrases, or related discourse. The technique of having a pupil read the same material again and over until their reading is fluent and error-free is known as RR. Also, RR is a teaching method that helps learners improve their oral reading skills. Learners are given numerous chances to practice reading aloud passages at their independent reading level, with teachers providing helpful comments after each chance. According to the description of RR, it is “a supplemental reading program that comprises of repeating a short and meaningful piece until an appropriate degree of fluency is achieved” (Samuels, 1979, p. 404).

RR is an effective strategy for students who have reading challenges to compete favorably with those who do not (Huang, Brett, & Diana, 2008). The RR method helps learners decode accurately and at a consistent rate. “Samuels (1979) ‘repeated readings’ approach is based on automaticity theory and the basic concept that “practice makes perfect.”

2.1.2.2. Effectiveness of RR

“Repeating readings help learners to build prosody, identify acceptable wording, and assess meaning,” Kuhn et al. (2010) add (p.233). Curtis (2004) also recognizes RR as a highly successful method for improving fluency in both older and younger learners. They say that RR may be accomplished by accelerated practice of letters, syllables, words, and phrases, or by reading the same material again and over until the pre-determined requirements are met (as cited in Curtis, 2004).

Reading can be a pleasurable and enjoyable pastime, and individuals who had difficulties with comprehension may progress and tend to more successful readers with tailored training. Reading techniques may be used to help all learners, but notably those who struggle with reading, improve their comprehension to have better performance for score achievements.

2.1.3. Audio modeling

Using visuals such as images, graphs, charts, models, and audio aids to reading can assist promote greater understanding. In addition, by combining digital reading with audiobooks, students' comprehension may be improved, and their literacy experience can be enhanced. Furthermore, the audiobook not only encourages young people to read, but it also assists struggling readers in persevering and finally mastering the amazing skill of reading a book (Baird, n.d.). Speaking by native speakers, excellent articulation and pronunciation, the greatest alternative to reading, available anytime, anywhere, and free online resources are just a few of the benefits of audiobooks for EFL learners. Because the abilities required for listening comprehension may also be applied to reading comprehension, audio is useful in improving EFL students' receptive skills.

Furthermore, audio not only aided in the promotion of higher-level components of the reading process, but also aided in the motivation of teenagers to read. Moreover, with the audio and its text, learners will be able to read in a multimodal manner. Additionally, the audio promotes auditory learners and aids their literacy development in order to increase text comprehension to achieve higher scores of test.

2.2. PREVIOUS STUDIES

The constructivist method, as applied in psychology, was founded by Jean Piaget and outlines one of the ways in which information may be gained throughout the learning process (Danforth and Smith, 2005). As a result, the theory can be immediately applicable in the classroom. Learning, according to the constructivist view, is a process that includes active involvement in order to generate meaning from the experiences that learners encounter. Accordingly, students learn best when they are forced to extract meaning on their own from a particular experience, with the instructor leading them through the process rather than explaining the meaning. The constructivist method involves both the student and the instructor. They each play a distinct function. Besides, Fosnot (1989) emphasized that a teacher should evaluate the experiences that students bring to the table as well as the information they accumulate from those experiences. Teachers assist students in gaining new ideas and information through their experiences.

Learners are expected to take initiative and actively engage in the acquisition of information (Fosnot, 1989). Each learner should combine new information with their current grasp of the subject. Learners must reflect on and extract information from their experiences in order to have control over their learning process. Huang (2009) stated that using RR as a way of improving reading comprehension is a practical application of constructivism theory. According to the notion, frequent reading entails the learners' active participation in the acquisition of knowledge. A student uses RR to read a passage until he or she can read it accurately and understand it in terms of meaning and grammatical points.

Silent reading, as well as reading comprehension was essential for EFL learners. In a study by Shimono T. R. (2018), his study indicates that students' rate gains were high, it was from 13 to 17 words every minute. However, learners may not understand the meaning of words in some specific contexts within silent reading. Laberge and Samuels (1974) show that many students realize reading difficulty in understanding the semantic units of phrases or sentences in texts relating to the low-level reading process and semantic sides. Therefore, this paper will focus on the use of the audio model with RR. It helps learners understand more obviously and be easy to concentrate on reading tasks.

RR is assumed as the basis with the idea of the reader's fluency being improved through reading a text repetitiously. As cited in Raney and Rayner (1995), the duration of reading can be shortened when a learner is made to do reading of a text or a word for the second time. An example is that if the learner carries on the reading within five minutes, the reading for the second time is anticipated to be less, which is considered as an advantage of repetition (Raney, Therriault, & Minkoff, 2000). Therefore, RR is to support the reader with the practice in context for the text. When the reader goes through the text repetitiously, the learner can become familiar with the words and sentences appearing in the text as well as structures of the text and semantic units. In RR, the first reading plays an important role as a foundation for the readings to go, and the reader can read the text much more fluently thanks to transferring the experience of reading that the learner has accumulated during the first reading to the second reading.

Different research projects have been invested in both L1 and L2 contexts to identify the effects of repeated reading on reading fluency and reading comprehension. Repeated Reading is based on the theory of automatic information processing first introduced by Laberge and Samuels (1974). This model is an automatic process of accurately decoding the text and simply comprehend the text rapidly. In EFL, the use of Repeated Reading has been less extensively applied (cited in Taguchi, Gorsuch, and Sasamoto, 2006) and the results of prior researches are various in terms of the differences of the treatment group with Repeated Reading method and the control group without using this method. Koskinen and Blum (1984) prove that Repeated Reading affects positively on the development of readers' vocabulary. Besides, Repeated Reading seems to be an effective method to support readers read phrases that are longer, including more syntactic and phonetic units (cited in Dowhower, 1987).

Some researchers have reported the neural result of the effects of Repeated Reading on reading comprehension. Chang (2012) proves the improvement of the reading rate for Repeated Reading group did not negatively impact on reading comprehension. The results highly support the positive effects of RR on reading teaching. The reading comprehension result from oral reading passages that Jeon (2012) collects is not clearly defined because of the participant lacking skills.

However, Chang and Millett (2013) provide clear evidence of the improvement in reading rates and reading comprehension. In reading rates, participants in the experimental group increased 47 words and 45 words per minute in the practiced texts and unpracticed texts, respectively in comparison with the control group without using Repeated Reading only increased 13 and 7 words. Repeated Reading students gained 19% and 17% for practiced texts and unpracticed texts in terms of reading comprehension. The results highly support the positive effects of Repeated Reading on reading teaching and this can facilitate learners.

Through four decades, Repeated Reading has developed more different versions, one of them is scaffolding with the audio model or assisted reading audio. The term scaffolding was invented by Wood, Bruner, and Ross (1976), it is referred to the construction support in building a new structure. In teaching, it is help from the teacher temporarily to guide learners to accomplish

tasks. In the research of Taguchi, Takayasu-Maass, and Gorsuch (2004), the extension of Repeated Reading treatment period from 10 to 17 weeks with the increase of session from 28 to 42, the authors find Repeated Reading with repetition and audio model support readers comprehension of L2 texts. Taguchi, Gorsuch, Takayasu-Maass, and Snipp (2012) used the auditory reading model from recording texts with multiple readers, including sound effects, to scaffold readers. The result is progressive in terms of reading comprehension enhancement, Naomi explains the scaffolding may connect readers' reading ability with their future reading ability, so Naomi could identify which parts in the text she understood with what she had not. The result is reported to be also positive in Gorsuch, Taguchi, & Umehara (2015). Shimono (2018) exposes the improvement after using Repeated Reading treatment, about 70% in comprehension percentage.

According to Laberge & Samuels (1974), reading involves two processes: low-level and high-level. The low-level process focuses on word recognition, syntactic parsing which requires readers skills-oriented. Also, as cited in Perfetti (2007), he emphasized that word recognition is one significant factor of the lower-level process in L2 reading, this element directs the learner to recognize the lexical meaning at a high level while reading. In addition, Rasinki (2014) indicated that students should be involved to vocabulary and word patterns to produce automaticity, and thus, word identification will be developed obviously. William J. Therrien (2015) illustrates that Repeated Reading gives a substantial improvement on word identification as well as decoding skills by giving learners a variety of exposures to similar words. Once students are fluent in reading the words, their fluency will be enhanced markedly, which develops and improves the understanding of the text.

To achieve the purpose of this proposal, the primary focus here relates to the semantics units understanding in texts, the first stage to proceed then next one. This is because semantic processing is an important contributor to reading comprehension and it is finally vocabulary that strongly controls semantic processing (cited in Koda, 1994, p. 10). Additionally, Balota (1990) indicated that word reading effectiveness is largely affected by semantic variables. This process is the requirement for a high-level reading process involving understanding text meaning, interpreting, applying background knowledge and evaluating the text's information. However, most previous research papers investigated the reading comprehension at the high-level process - comprehension rather than low-level process. The students in grade 10 class struggle with the first process to proceed to the next stage. Therefore, it is important to apply Repeated Reading to identify readers' ability after using this method because of its potential results.

2.2.1 Advantages and disadvantages of RR

2.2.1.1 Merits of RR in reading comprehension

When applying this method in teaching, its advantages are essential to consider in dealing with understanding the problems of grade tenth students. In the research of Taguchi, Takayasu-Maass, and Gorsuch (2004) six out of ten participants commented Repeated Reading that motivated them more in reading long passages. They also state that another benefit could get from Repeated Reading is guessing the meaning of unknown words or phrases in texts. The similar result has been identified eight years later, the research of Taguchi, Takayasu-Maass, Gorsuch and Snipp (2012) Naomi as a participant also appreciates the benefit of the enhances comprehension of single sentences and discourse, particularly, guessing the meaning of unknown words or phrases with ambiguous grammatical points. Besides, Repeated Reading supports readers to remember vocabulary and recall meanings of words in later readings within Repeated Reading sessions. Based on these benefits, it is appropriate for grade 10 students to deal with understanding problems. When applying the audio model, the reader seems to read slightly faster than without audio models. Cohen (2011) also emphasizes that with the role of an instructional design, Repeated Reading performs well for the attainment of short-term goals such as understanding the text more obviously and reading it more accurately and quickly.

2.2.1.2 Demerits of RR in reading comprehension

Although Repeated Reading method brings learners various advantages but there are also some drawbacks needing to review. Taguchi, Takayasu- Maass, Gorsuch and Snipp (2012) reveal the boring and demotivating feeling in readers when using Repeated Reading method and the limitations of comprehension at a higher level. With the audio model, the reader does understand the meaning of unknown vocabulary and ambiguous grammatical points in tests.

From reviewing the literature, different researchers provide various views of Repeated Reading in their contexts. Most results indicate the effectiveness of Repeated Reading in improving understating phrases and single sentences while reading. Therefore, it is appropriate to apply in grade 10 students in Vo Minh Duc high school as a suitable solution.

2.2.2. RR strategies and high school education

RR in high school has resulted in significant improvements in the efficacy of reading teaching across the world. There are two primary approaches to assess the effectiveness of RR procedures. The first technique is based on automated word processing, while the second is based on the impact of contextual linguistics on reading efficiency (Therrien & Kubina, 2006). Reading on a regular basis develops a habit that aids with language comprehension (Omer, 2011). To increase the efficacy of RR, a variety of methods can be used. RRs have been found to be beneficial to high school students with learning difficulties.

Some methods offered include utilizing the approach as a supplement, employing reading materials suited for the learners' reading level, and applying systematic error corrections, particularly for miscued words, to achieve optimal performance (Alber-Morgan, 2006). On the other hand, as evidenced by the literature review, RR methods are becoming increasingly successful in developing better levels of knowledge in any given situation.

2.2.3. *RR strategy with audio modeling*

Oddo et al. (2010) go through some of the most useful reading methods for RR. In terms of material comprehension and retention, the use of peer-mediated RR produced some of the greatest outcomes among the individuals in the study. Begeny, et al. (2009) claimed that among the three techniques for improving comprehension, RR with audio is the most beneficial. RR with audio while reading was found to be beneficial in increasing reading comprehension in a group of learners by Rasinski (1989).

Reading and listening to text has a variety of advantages, especially for youngsters who struggle to concentrate on reading activities. Reading and listening help students improve their English language skills (syntax, pronunciation, emphasis, etc). Students that listened to the audiobook had higher reading comprehension abilities. In addition, audio can also be utilized as supplementary resources in advanced foreign language reading and listening classes, based on the research of audio-based RR' effects on reading comprehension and students' opinions on utilizing audio with RR in classroom settings to enhance learners' reading skill.

The RR with audio appropriate for use in elementary, secondary, middle, high school, and university settings. That is due to the significant contrasts between reading with audiobooks and conventional reading aloud, such as the fact that reading with audiobooks is not limited by time or place and can be done anywhere using portable devices; second, thanks to its ease and simplicity, reading becomes more pleasant since good novels are professionally narrated by prominent actors, including the writers themselves, and offering learners proper word pronunciation through native speakers' narrators. Additionally, combining listening and reading improves reading comprehension. Listening to and following the reading material improves decoding abilities and vocabulary, which helps with reading.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

This chapter offers an overview of the study's research methodology. It includes details on the participants, such as the study's qualifying requirements, who the participants were, and how they were chosen. The researcher discusses why the research design he employed for this study was chosen. The equipment that was utilized to collect data, as well as the procedures employed to perform this study, are also described. The methodology for data analysis is also described by the researcher.

3.1. RESEARCH METHODS

After interviewing four English teachers who are currently teaching grade 10 students and observing students in those classes, a detailed plan will be planned for research. This research conducted quantitative research method. In the social sciences, quantitative technique is the most used research framework. It is a set of methods, methodologies, and assumptions that are used to investigate psychological, social, and economic processes using mathematical patterns. Quantitative research collects a wide range of numerical information. Numeric data is naturally quantitative in certain situations, whereas numeric organization is imposed in others. Researchers can use quantitative data to undertake simple to very advanced statistical studies that aggregate data, highlight correlations between data, and compare across aggregated data. Questionnaires, organized observations, and experiments are examples of quantitative research techniques. This study conducts pre-test and post-test, questionnaire survey to examine the effect of audio-based RR on Grade 10 high school students as well as uses semi opened-ended-question interview to explore advantages and disadvantages of RR on these EFL learners.

3.2. POPULATION AND SAMPLING

The whole grade tenth in Vo Minh Duc high school consists of 481 students (63% are female students and 47% are male students) distributed into 13 classes. In the sample of the study, two intact groups which had the average scores from the entrance examination of Vo Minh Duc High School. These two classes chosen from a list of classes include 76 students from two classes with 39 students of 10A5 class (15 males and 24 females) assigned the experimental group and 37 students of 10A6 class (12 males and 25 females) assigned the control group, respectively. Each of the two intact classes was randomly assigned pre-tests and post-tests. For justification of the choice of grade 10, they have just passed the entrance exam to high school and seem not to follow a new curriculum. Also, a list of students who achieved average scores will be conducted to show that they have problems with reading comprehension with mistakes relating to semantic parts. Therefore, it is appropriate to implement a treatment to improve their reading comprehension as well as enhance the ability to understand semantic units in texts.

3.3. A DESCRIPTION OF THE POPULATION

All 76 participants in this study were weak at reading skill. They had low scores with reading exercises. Some students interviewed answered that they found that reading skill boring because it was first time-consuming. They showed that they were often distracted and hard to concentrate on passages in reading class. Another reason was that they found reading activities boring because there was no advancement in reading methods. The population chosen was appropriate for the study because they were not good at reading comprehension and might have difficulties with text understanding.

3.4. RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS

Semantic understanding tests was implemented for both pre-tests and post-tests. A questionnaire survey is used with 10 statements to investigate the effectiveness of audio-based RR on EFL learners' reading comprehension. Finally, an interview designed with 4 main questions, which are semi opened-ended, is employed to collect quantitative data. Materials were used in a quasi-experimental research design, including *Time Zones 3* and semantic understanding tests. The *Time Zones 3* course consists of 12 units with audio files and each unit contains one passage for the experimental group and the control group. This book is for A2 level with reading passages from 250 to 300 words, the same language focus with grade-tenth students so they could practice combining syntax and semantics during reading sessions.

3.5. DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURES

All participants were introduced clearly about the purpose of the study to ensure their respect for the research process, testing results. The entire procedure was obviously explained and carefully in the instructions, and no cheating was allowed in research tests. The proctors were teachers in this high school. In addition, they were also clearly instructed to keep the tests and seriously administer the testing rooms in both pre-tests and post-tests.

As the implementation of primary data, participants from both the experimental group and the control group undertook an instrument using semantic understanding tests in the first week of the study. To have an equal chance and results, the method intended to combine test A (Appendix A) and test B (Appendix B) for both pre-tests and post-tests together and delivered to 76 participants of two classes. The two kinds of test were counterbalanced and delivered to participants. Therefore, if a student received a test A as a pre-test, that student was given test B as a post-test. To make sure the distribution to be reliable, a list of participants was conducted, and a specific number was assigned to each of the students. The seat arrangement was maintained for the latter purpose.

After collecting the scores from the pre-tests results, SPSS (The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) was used to compare the means of two groups of the study. SPSS standing for The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences is a software package used in statistical analysis. In this case, Independent Samples T-Test was used to compare means and disparity between the experimental group and the control group. The purpose of this step of the analysis was to seek whether the level of one group was the same as the other one or not.

For the experimental group, a treatment used underwent 12 weeks of the experiment. Thirty-nine students in the experimental group were taught by Repeated Reading method using passages in each unit with the support of an audio model with the coursebook called *Time Zones 3*, including 12 units for 12-week practicing – one read text for a one-week session (used for secondary data). For the control group, 37 participants were taught with the same coursebook but with a different method. Students from this group were only taught by silent reading without the assistance of an audio model.

After 12-week applying the treatment to the experimental group, the opened- ended-question interview was carried on with the experimental group to collect quantitative data to investigate pros and cons of the treatment.

After that, the instrument came later with randomly post-tests' distribution once again. The list of numbers of students was used to make sure that positions and test distribution to participants are equal. Therefore, if the participant received a previous test as a pre-test, he/she received a post- test at this time. After that, semantic tests were collected from both groups.

3.6. DATA ANALYSIS METHODS

To measure the level of two groups, an instrument using pre- and post-tests distribution randomly was collected and SPSS was used to analyze means from both groups of participants. In SPSS, Independent Samples T-Test was undertaken to make a comparison of the level of two groups. In case all 76 participants were from closely similar levels in the pre-test, a treatment was considered more reliable. If the participants' level was significantly discrepant, this could lead to the prediction of results with test covariate. The Independent Samples T-Test also compared post-tests of two groups, it is also expected to witness a significant change of scores in post-tests between the experimental group and the control one.

The data values from pre-tests and post-tests were continuously analyzed by implementing the Paired Samples T-Test. The purpose of this was to seek discrepancy pre-tests and post-test in the experimental group. Also, it is expected that the use of Paired Samples T-Test for the control group could witness no significant changes. From this justification, the treatment was reliable and proved that it can improve learners' understanding of semantic units in texts after a 12-week experiment.

After analyzing data from SPSS, the results were processed and analyzed the effectiveness of the treatment and feedback from participants. Another perspective was undertaken, for outliers having achieved the too high scores or slow scores from the instrument, information was gathered and recorded to plan another action research for newly-born problems.

After collecting all necessary for the first round in research, the whole process was looked back to evaluate the results within the effects of different covariates. In this case, relative literature was reviewed and suitable methods were extracted to improve these issues and devise a new plan to solve the problems. These classes were used in the next round or some special cases only, probably further studies.

With the disadvantages of understanding semantic units, phrases and sentences in texts while reading, it hindered EFL learners from solving reading tasks as well as comprehending semantic aspects. For learners to be able to reach the study, the sample through an interview with school teachers was chosen to find suitable classes, and a study was conducted after the first semester. This study made an effort to prove that Repeated Reading can affect students' semantic unit-understanding ability.

CHAPTER 4: DATA ANALYSIS

The outcomes of several research methodologies were presented in this chapter. After gathering data, the chapter provided a comprehensive examination of research equipment.

4.1. PRE-TEST

After all pre-tests were collected from control participants and participants from treatment group. SPSS was used to analyze collected data and the results were interpreted into percentages. The table and figure below presented analyzed results from the control group:

Table 4.1. Results of pre-test (control group)
pre1

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	<=5	28	75.7	75.7	75.7
	6	7	18.9	18.9	94.6
	7	1	2.7	2.7	97.3
	8	1	2.7	2.7	100.0
Total		37	100.0	100.0	

As can be obviously presented from the table below, nearly 76% of participants in the control group achieving ≤ 5 and this number represented 28 individuals. Besides, the number of control students receiving 6 from pre-test was just 7 students, making it make up 18.9%. Beside that, this ranked the second position in this table. The percentage of participants achieving scores ranging from 7 to 8 occupied the same rate of 2.7%, making it the lowest proportion in total.

Fig 4.1. Pie chart of pre-test in control group

As looking at the pie chart, the percentage for score of 5 occupied the largest segment of the chart while that for 8 just became the smallest slice contributing to the results of pre-test in this control group. Noticeably, there was no appearance of scores 9 and 10. To dominate the second place, the percentage of score of 6 exhibited itself as the second largest part of the chart.

Similarly, the experimental participants were administrated the pre-test at the same time. The table and figure below reflected their analyzed results categorized into percentage and frequency.

Table 4.2. Results of pre-test (experimental group)

pre1		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	<=5	28	71.8	71.8	71.8
	6	7	17.9	17.9	89.7
	7	2	5.1	5.1	94.9
	8	1	2.6	2.6	97.4
	9	1	2.6	2.6	100.0
Total		39	100.0	100.0	

Generally speaking, score 5 dominated the highest position with 71.8% of participants receiving ≤ 5 , which numerated 28 individuals. Additionally, score 6 remained itself as the second highest category with 17.9% in the table. The percentage of students achieving scores of 7 and 8 accounted for low percentages of 5.1% and 2.6%, respectively. Finally, noticeably, score of 9 did appear in this group but just made up 2.6% with only 1 student who performed on the pre-test.

The figure below provided a detailed demonstration about results analyzed from pre-test.

Fig 4.2. Pie chart of pre-test in experimental group

The above-presented figure showed an equivalent pattern as compared to the results of control group. The proportion of under 5 dominated the largest slice of the chart. The proportions for scores ranging between 6 and 7 held places with the second largest and third largest segment illustrated in the circle. Last but not least, the proportion of participants with 8 and 9 shared the same size of slice with 2.56%.

Furthermore, Independent Samples *t*-Test was used with the purpose of making a comparison about the scores of pre-tests between the control group and the experimental group. The Independent Samples *t*-Test analyzes the means of two independent groups to see if statistical evidence exists that the related population means differ substantially. A parametric test is the Independent Samples *t*-Test. In this case of study, The Independent Samples *t*-Test is used to compare the means of two groups statistically.

Table 4.3. Independent Samples t-Test comparing pre-tests

Group Statistics					
	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
pre_test	control	37	4.16	1.803	.296
	exp	39	4.59	1.802	.289

Independent Samples Test	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
pre_test Equal variances assumed	.002	.963	-	74	.305	-.428	.414	-1.252	.397
			-	73.787	.305	-.428	.414	-1.252	.397
Equal variances not assumed			1.034						

As can be obviously reported from the SPSS, mean (M) of pre-test in the control group was 4.16 while M of pre-test in experimental group was 4.59. generally, the Mean score between two groups did not show significant disparity. As presented in the Std. Deviation, the disparity between two groups was just 0.001, indicating modest disparity of pre-test. The second table showed a more detailed analysis, sig. (2-tailed) with t = 0.305 which was larger than 0.05. From this observation, score between the control and experimental group was not different from each other.

4.2. QUESTIONNAIRE

Following the pre-test, all 39 participants in the experimental group undertook the questionnaire survey consisting of 10 statements, the questionnaire was also designed based on Likert scale. Here were results from surveyed questionnaire. For eligible reference, valid was used for labeling the statement in the questionnaire as below:

- Sta.1: I was engaged more effectively in reading materials with audio-basedRR than silent reading.
- Sta.2: I was able to assess the meaning of unknown words more relatively accurately thanks to audio-based RR.
- Sta.3: The treatment increased not only reading comprehension but also listening skill as well.
- Sta.4: The treatment not only improved accurate pronunciation but also increased reading fluency.
- Sta.5. The treatment facilitated me to do reading tasks more quickly than silent reading.
- Sta.6. The treatment provided me a multimodal reading experience, which helped me avoid frustration in reading.
- Sta.7. RR provided me a substantial improvement on word identification as well as decoding skills by giving a variety of exposures to similar words.
- Sta.8. The treatment helped me read phrases that were longer, including more syntactic and phonetic units.
- Sta.9. The treatment taught me to guess the meaning of unknown words or phrases with ambiguous grammatical points.
- Sta.10. The treatment raised learner autonomy more effectively.

Table 4.4. Results from Sta.1 and Sta.2

Sta.1		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	22	56.4	56.4	56.4
	Agree	11	28.2	28.2	84.6
	Neutral	3	7.7	7.7	92.3
	Disagree	2	5.1	5.1	97.4
	Strongly disagree	1	2.6	2.6	100.0
	Total	39	100.0	100.0	
Sta.2		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	15	38.5	38.5	38.5
	Agree	14	35.9	35.9	74.4
	Neutral	5	12.8	12.8	87.2
	Disagree	4	10.3	10.3	97.4
	Strongly disagree	1	2.6	2.6	100.0
	Total	39	100.0	100.0	

As exhibited above, the percentage of participants reporting to Sta.1 with strong agreement accounted for 56.4% while 28.2% of participants saying that they agreed with the first statement that RR with audio was effective than silent reading. Only 1 student claimed that the treatment was not more effective than silent reading with 2.6% of total. Meanwhile, referring to Sta.2, the proportion of students believing that they were able to assess the meaning of unfamiliar word more effectively represented

38.5% for strong agreement and 35.9% for agreement, respectively. There were just 12.8% not showing their own opinion. The percentage of strong disagreement for Sta.2 just occupied 2.6% as well.

Table 4.5. Results from Sta.3 and Sta.4

Sta.3		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	16	41.0	41.0	41.0
	Agree	9	23.1	23.1	64.1
	Neutral	10	25.6	25.6	89.7
	Disagree	3	7.7	7.7	97.4
	Strongly disagree	1	2.6	2.6	100.0
	Total	39	100.0	100.0	
Sta.4		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	22	56.4	56.4	56.4
	Agree	9	23.1	23.1	79.5
	Neutral	5	12.8	12.8	92.3
	Disagree	2	5.1	5.1	97.4
	Strongly disagree	1	2.6	2.6	100.0
	Total	39	100.0	100.0	

As reflected afore, the proportion of questionnaire takers responding to Sta.3 with strong agreement occupied 41.1% while 23.1% of participants reporting that they agreed that audio-based RR increased their listening skill as well. Only 1 student reported with strong disagreement with 2.6% of total. Meanwhile, taking a look at Sta.4, the proportion of students conducted that they could improve their fluency and also pronunciation represented 56.4% for strong agreement and 23.1% for agreement, respectively. Similarly, there were 12.8% not showing their own opinion. Finally, the percentage of strong disagreement for Sta.4 just occupied 2.6% as well, which was the same percentage as compared to Sta.3.

Table 4.6. Results from Sta.5 and Sta.6

Sta.5		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	16	41.0	41.0	41.0
	Agree	10	25.6	25.6	66.7
	Neutral	7	17.9	17.9	84.6
	Disagree	5	12.8	12.8	97.4
	Strongly disagree	1	2.6	2.6	100.0
	Total	39	100.0	100.0	
Sta.6		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	12	30.8	30.8	30.8
	Agree	17	43.6	43.6	74.4
	Neutral	6	15.4	15.4	89.7
	Disagree	3	7.7	7.7	97.4
	Strongly disagree	1	2.6	2.6	100.0
	Total	39	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.5 showed that the percentage of experimental participants giving response to Sta.5 with strong agreement made up exactly 41% while 25.6% reported that they agreed that audio-based RR helped participants performed the tasks more quickly. There was just 1 participant responding with strong disagreement with 2.6% in total. On the other hand, generally speaking in Sta.6, the percentage of questionnaire performers stating that the treatment provided us a multimodal reading experience, which helped us avoid frustration in reading occupied 30.8% for strong agreement and 43.6% for agreement, respectively. Similarly, there were 17.9% and 15.4% of participants who did not show either agreement and disagreement opinion for Sta.5 and Sta.6, respectively.

Table 4.7. Results from Sta.7 and Sta.8

Sta.7		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	11	28.2	28.2	28.2
	Agree	19	48.7	48.7	76.9
	Neutral	5	12.8	12.8	89.7
	Disagree	3	7.7	7.7	97.4

Strongly disagree	1	2.6	2.6	100.0	
Total	39	100.0	100.0		
Sta.8	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Valid	Strongly agree	17	43.6	43.6	43.6
	Agree	14	35.9	35.9	79.5
	Neutral	3	7.7	7.7	87.2
	Disagree	3	7.7	7.7	94.9
	Strongly disagree	2	5.1	5.1	100.0
	Total	39	100.0	100.0	

As illustrated in Table 4.5, experimental participants providing their response to Sta.7 with strong agreement accounted for 28.2% while 48.7% gave their agreement. There were just 3 participants disagreeing with 7.7% in total. Otherwise, in Sta.8, the proportion of experimental group strongly agreeing that the treatment helped us read phrases that were longer, including more syntactic and phonetic units making up 43.6% and 35.9% for agreement. Similarly, there were 7.7% of participants showing disagreement and neutral response for Sta.8, respectively. Remarkably, the percentage of students strongly disagreeing showed a higher figure than Sta.1 to Sta.7, accounting for 5.1% of total.

Table 4.8. Results from Sta.9 and Sta.10

Sta.9	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Valid	Strongly agree	14	35.9	35.9	35.9
	Agree	11	28.2	28.2	64.1
	Neutral	8	20.5	20.5	84.6
	Disagree	4	10.3	10.3	94.9
	Strongly disagree	2	5.1	5.1	100.0
	Total	39	100.0	100.0	
Sta.10	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Valid	Strongly agree	8	20.5	20.5	20.5
	Agree	10	25.6	25.6	46.2
	Neutral	15	38.5	38.5	84.6
	Disagree	3	7.7	7.7	92.3
	Strongly disagree	3	7.7	7.7	100.0
	Total	39	100.0	100.0	

As demonstrated above, the proportion of students responding to Sta.9 with strong agreement made up 35.9% while 28.2% of participants answering that they agreed with the ninth statement. Only 2 students strongly disagreed that the treatment taught them to guess the meaning of unknown words or phrases with ambiguous grammatical points. Meanwhile, analyzing Sta.10, the percentage of participants believing that the treatment raised their autonomy more effectively represented 20.5% for strong agreement and 25.6% for agreement, respectively. The percentage of strong disagreement for Sta.10 just occupied 7.7% as well.

4.3. INTERVIEW

Another instrument was used to collect data in this study was interview inform of semi opened-ended questions. All 39 participants were asked to undertake the interview comprising of 4 questions. Participants answered questions with response in form of numbers, phrases, or even sentences. Then, all answers of 39 participants were interpreted into phrases having the same themes. These themes were classified into questions where they were asked to explore.

What are the disadvantages did you have in the first week of treatment?

Fig 4.3. Results from Q1 of interview

As presented in column graph, participants were asked about drawbacks that they might experience in the first week of the treatment period. First, 41% of them said that they had no idea with the question, accounting for 16 participants of total. Meanwhile, 20.55 of interviewees reported that they had difficulties with comprehension at a higher level and this made up 8 students of total. At the first week, 9 participants claimed that they lost interest and motivation with the treatment, representing 23.1% in total. Also, “boring valid” occupied just 15.4% with 6 students reporting to the question.

What are the advantages did you have in the first week?

Figure 4.4. Results from Q2 of interview

On the other hand, as asked about benefits of audio-based RR in the first week, participants indicated more answers for advantages than disadvantages. First, 14 participants said that the treatment motivated them in reading longer passages with 35.9%. Likewise, the percentage of interviewees claimed that they were able to guess the unfamiliar words better accounted for the same proportion of the former one with 35.9%. These above answers shared the highest column in the bar chart. The treatment helped experimental group remember words longer with 7 students saying that, occupying 17.9% of total. Remarkably, there was just 1

student giving no idea to the question, which accounted for only 2.6%. Reading faster was reported to be one of the advantages that participants realized in the first week with 3 individuals that voted, making up 7.7% in the bar chart. To explore to see which point of time that participants found the treatment beneficial, Q3 was designed to investigate the numbers.

Figure 4.5. Results from Q3 of interview

As can be clearly shown that the number of students saying that they found audio-based RR advantages was 14 with the third- to fifth week, making up 14% of total. Meanwhile, “fourth- to tenth week” valid occupied 16 participants with exactly 41%, making it become the highest column. The quantity of experimental participants responding to this question with eighth- to eleventh week was just 5 and this accounted for 12.8% of total. Finally, only small number of interviewees found the last three weeks beneficial, which made up 4 people with 10.3% in the column graph. Finally, the last question in this interview was to ask an opposite pattern about in which weeks they felt the treatment difficult. The table below showed a clear illustration about the question.

Figure 4.6. Results from Q4 of interview

Taking a more detailed observation, the quantities of participants responding that they found audio-based RR difficult to be engaged was 19 with the first- to third week, accounting for 48.7% of total. Meanwhile, “second- to third weeks” valid occupied exactly 10 participants with exactly 25.6%, making it become the second highest column. The quantity of experimental participants responding to this question with third- to fifth week was 8 and this accounted for 20.5% of total. Finally, only small number of interviewees found the first week difficult to study with the treatment, which made up 2 people with 5.1% in the column graph.

4.4. POST-TEST

At the final stage of the treatment, post-test was employed to examine the effectiveness of audio-based RR to improve Vo Minh Duc high school students’ reading comprehension. All 76 participants were required to perform the post-test in term of multiple-choice question with 10 questions. Presented below were results from post-tests of two groups:

Figure 4.7. Results of post-test from control group

Generally categorizing, the percentage of participants in the control group achieving under 5 occupied 51.35%, making it become the largest segment of the circle. Meanwhile, there were 37.84% of them receiving 6 for post-test, and just 5.41% of control participants getting 7. The proportion of post-test takers achieving 8 and 9 shared the same rate with 2.7% of total.

On the other hand, experimental group had a better performance in post-test with changes in the percentage of post-test’s scores.

Figure 4.8. Results of post-test from experimental group

As illustrated clearly in the circle, experimental shared the circle with equivalently fair segments. First, the percentage for under 5 points just accounted for 15.38%. The proportions for scores 6,7, and 8 represented 17.95%, 25.64%, and 20.51%, respectively. Finally, the proportion of participants achieving 9 made up 12.82% while that for 10 released 7.695 of total. Additionally, another Independent Samples t-Test was shown to examine the difference between two groups after taking post-test:

Table 4.9. Independent Samples t-Test of Post-test Group Statistics

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
post_t est	control	37	4.95	1.855	.305
	exp	39	7.05	1.776	.284

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
Independent Test	Samples	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
post_t est	Equal variances assumed	.096	.758	-5.054	74	.000	-2.105	.417	-2.935	-1.275
	Equal variances not assumed			-5.048	73.315	.000	-2.105	.417	-2.936	-1.274

As shown above, M value of the control group with post-test was 4.95 while that of experimental group was 7.05. Apparently, the Mean value between two groups showed a significant disparity. Besides, Sig. (2-tailed) with $t = 0.000 < 0.05$, it is therefore concluded that the experimental group did the post-test better than the control group.

Additionally, Paired Samples t-Test was applied to compare the results between pre-test and post-test in one group to examine the development. Shown below was the result for control group:

Table 4.10. Paired Samples t-Test (control group) Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair1 pre_test	4.16	37	1.803	.296
post_test	4.95	37	1.855	.305

Paired Samples Test	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 pre_test - post_test	-.784	1.294	.213	-1.215	-.352	-3.685	36	.001

As reported for the control group. In particular, MEAN of pre-test was 4.16 while that of post-test was 4.95. Therefore, it can be conducted that control participants did not show significant improvement.

Another Paired Samples t-Test was set for experimental group:

Table 4.11. Paired Samples t-Test (experimental group)

Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 pre_test	4.59	39	1.802	.289
post_test	7.05	39	1.776	.284

Paired Samples Test	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 pre_test - post_test	-2.462	1.253	.201	-2.868	-2.055	-12.265	38	.000

As observed above, MEAN of pre-test in this group was 4.59 and after 12 weeks of the intervention of audio-based RR treatment, MEAN of post-test was 7.05. Besides, sig. with $t = 0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, it can be conducted that the experimental group had strongly significant improvement in reading comprehension thanks to the treatment.

CHAPTER 5: FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings from the study instruments used to gather and analyze the data were provided in this chapter, as well as a discussion of the findings. Also, this chapter includes a thorough presentation and discussion of the data analysis as well as the study's findings.

5.1. FINDINGS FROM PRE-TEST

In the first week of the action research project, I distributed the permission to the schoolboard to be accepted to do the study, and also delivered the purpose of this study to the teachers as stakeholders. I found that 100% teachers as well as the principal agreed with the study. Besides, when I introduced the purpose and the reasons to do this research, all students revealed their excitement and they reported that they were willing to become the participants in the research. Following this, I referred to the scores of the two classes chosen for the research participation from entrance exam, and I realized that the scores between two groups were significantly similar to each other. Subsequently, I began to examine the two groups with pre-tests and found that all 76 participants were ready to take the test because they had just passed the entrance exam, so I believed that they had knowledge and felt willing enough to undergo the test. After the pre-tests, the scores reflected so many points which were not only similar to their ability for the entrance exam scores but also shown some interesting pictures. First, when analyzing scores from pre-tests, I found that two third of participants in the control group achieved under 5 points out of 10 questions, which indicated they did not perform well on the test for reading section. Also, from the teacher administrating the pre-test date, she reported me that some students did the test very fast within a half of given time. Additionally, the number of studentstaking Test A were higher than that taking Test B. Also from the pre-tests, the results exhibited that only over 20% of the control group were good readers. On the other hand, the results of pre-tests from the experimental group reflected that the number of students achieving over 5 points was a little more than the control group, however, this did not affect the effectiveness the intervention of the study. Generally, there was not a significant discrepancy between the two groups in their reading pre-tests.

5.2. FINDINGS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Ten statements were designed for questionnaire survey, collected results indicated great findings to examine the effectiveness of audio-based RR on EFL learners' reading comprehension. Almost over 50% of each statement were dominated by strong agreement as well as agreement. The majority of experimental participants believed that the treatment had a significant impact to their reading competence. From results of post-test (see Figure 4.7), participants in the experimental group did improve their reading comprehension with higher scores, as compared with a modest advancement from the control participants (see Figure 4.6). Besides, the percentage of opinions including neutral, disagreement and strong disagreement just showed percentages which were far lower than the survey's total percentage of strong agreement and agreement. From this view, the treatment group reported that audio-based RR affected significantly to their reading comprehension and raised reading scores.

5.3. FINDINGS FROM THE INTERVIEW

Further findings were seen in interview session, this was to investigate the advantages and disadvantages of the treatment. The questions were designed as semi opened-ended items. Therefore, the answers were collected and classified into pros group and cons groups. The interview revealed apparently that the beneficial sides of the treatment did outweigh its deleterious sides as participants showed more upsides than downsides. Also, almost interviewees said that they received benefits from the treatment from fourth week to tenth week (see Figure 4.5). Hence, it can be understood that the treatment benefited participants a period of 7 weeks, which was long enough to reach the effectiveness more appropriately.

5.4. FINDINGS FROM POTS-TEST

After the completion of the intervention routine lasting 12 weeks with 12 units, post-tests were applied to examine the improvement. My first expectation was that I hypothesized the scores of the post-tests in the experimental group would be better than that of the pre-tests. The results indicated what I expected. First, there was a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the experimental group, the score performance of the post-tests was as great as I expected. The method of audio-based RR led to advancements in reading comprehension. Particularly, the percentage of students achieving over 5 points on the post-tests occupied 84.62% of total. More surprisingly, the percentage for scores in terms of under 5 of the post-tests decreased significantly by 56.41%, compared with 24.33% of the pre-tests. The results indicated that after the use of audio-based RR, the percentage of students achieving ranging 8 to 10 points increased relatively, which indicated that the treatment raised their improvement on reading comprehension. This suggested that the treatment of audio-based RR particularly contributed to the reading improvement of the students in the experimental group. On the other hand, a comparison of the pre-test and post-test scores of the control group indicated that the percentages of students having under 5 points fell insignificant, still remaining a half of the group to be under 5. The percentage of students receiving high scores ranging from 7 to 9 was modest, which showed that they performed less improvement than the experimental group.

5.5. RELATIONSHIP TO LITERATURE REVIEW

Referring to the study of Taguchi, Takayasu-Maass, Gorsuch and Snipp (2012), the study that I conducted indicated the equivalent cases. Participants easily got bored and demotivated, they felt difficult in understanding the meaning of unknown words and felt confused when they had to listen to words that seemed unfamiliar to them. Nevertheless, the majority of participants revealed more advantageous sides towards audio-based RR than its disadvantages as interviewed.

From my point of view, EFL learners usually need to study with such a strategy, such as RR with audio, to solve their difficulties in reading learning. Also, this strategy remarkably helps learners improve their scores and facilitate their reading comprehension. Hence, the results from this study proved the effectiveness as well as the positive impact of audio-based RR in the improvement of reading comprehension. Additionally, this study's results emphasized that RR strategy with audio is necessary for students in grade 10 to provide them concrete foundation for the next curriculum.

5.6. DISCUSSION

The purpose of this research was to examine the effects of the RR strategy with audio on 10th grade students' reading comprehension in Vo Minh Duc High School. At this view of the thesis, I will discuss about the connection between the findings of this study and the previous literature review, limitations and future directions of this study. After the study, I found that participants in the experimental group performed more significantly on the post-tests as compared to the students in the control group who shown no considerable improvements. Throughout the treatment, I found that students in the experimental group performed better on post-tests than those in the control group, who showed no significant changes. Besides, participants in the experimental group with the treatment improved their level of reading comprehension because they were able to recognize and understand better the syntax of the word, which was shown on the scores of the post-tests. My findings reinforced the previous literature review, which emphasized that RR method impacted significantly on the performance of learners. Additionally, audio-based RR enhanced learning competence and also reading skills of participants in high school while the normal method hinders learners to understand new vocabulary and probably does not provide them an opportunity to discover the meaning of the words which make them feel hard to understand while reading. Thus, audio-based RR played an essential role in helping learners understand the reading.

The RR technique was shown to be successful in the study. An examination of the data reveals that the experimental group's grades increased steadily from pre-test to post-test. The participants in the control group did not demonstrate any significant increase in their test results, but the students who received RR instruction improved their test scores. It showed that the majority of learners in a class benefit from the RR approach. However, when comparing the pre-test and post-test scores, it is clear that the RR approach improves the majority of students' comprehension ability. When comparing the pretest and post-test, my analysis revealed a substantial increase, which means that there was a disparity between two tests.

Students who employed this technique, on the other hand, increased their reading comprehension because they were able to comprehend vocabulary and the language's structure. My findings corroborate prior research, which found that the RR technique of learning had a substantial favorable influence on students' performance. Furthermore, the RR technique enhances high school students' learning capacities and reading skills, but the traditional method inhibits learners from comprehending and absorbing new words and does not allow them to investigate the meaning of words they may encounter when reading. As a result, the teaching approach has a significant impact on students' comprehension of the content and academic success.

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION

The key findings, as well as the study's limitations and future research goals, were presented in this chapter. The chapter concluded with some recommendations for instructors and students as well as implications.

6.1. SUMMARY OF THE MAIN FINDINGS

As referred to research question 1 “To what extent does Audio-based RR improve learners’ reading comprehension?”, the results from my study revealed that there was a significant improvement in the experimental group that was taught with the treatment of RR. The results shown that the control group which did not receive the treatment performed lower scores because this group was taught with normal reading teaching methodology, it was possibly called silent reading. Meanwhile, the experimental group with audio-based RR indicated more significant results. First, their scores rose remarkably after the intervention. This exhibited that the treatment improved reading competence of participants. Secondly, participants with the treatment shown their interest in reading routine with more discussion and concentration. In other words, a strong comparison of the proportion of change between the experimental group and the control group reflected that the participants performed better in terms of understanding semantic units of the reading tests and proportions of reading accuracy as compared to the control group using normal RR, the experimental group had higher attainments than the control group.

Besides, quantitative data from interview reflected positively that nearly 97% of participants in the experimental group agreed the benefits of audio- based RR that have brought sincere changes. Particularly, in the third and fourth week of the treatment, 20% participants showed that they were still unfamiliar with the treatment and felt difficult in catching up with the speed as well as comprehension of the technique. However, in later weeks of the intervention, they indicated that the method highly impacted their critical thinking and their reading competence.

In addition, some participants wrote their views about the advantages of RR. Some agreed that the treatment also raised their reading speed after the sixth to ninth week. Furthermore, their reading confidence increased relatively, they reported that reading became more approachable and easier to understand semantic units in reading text. They indicated that RR with audio helped them have better comprehension and had better connection to the text, which facilitated the learners to understand deeply the content of the reading. Moreover, some information revealed in interview exhibited that RR with audio-built sight word vocabulary more effectively.

The research indicated that audio-based RR method was effective. The data collected exhibited that the experimental group had a relative growth in their marks from pre-test to post-test. The control group of participants did not indicate any considerable improvement in their test scores, while the participants that were taught with audio-based RR training produced better test scores with expected scores.

I also found out that the percentage of students in the control group not achieving 8 to 10 points remained the same as the pre-test. However, as compared to the experimental group, the percentage of participants receiving 8 to 10 points increased relatively. Further analysis of the quantitative data exhibited that the majority of students of the control group did not show scores better in the post-test.

Additionally, noticeably in the tenth week, I realized that the majority of participants in the treatment group were able to discuss positively about the reading and also, they exchanged their ideas about the meaning of vocabulary after the audio was played. Whereas, the atmosphere in the control group’s class was quiet, which showed that with the reading-learning process, students got demotivated and did not get involved in an effective learning environment. The results indicated that audio-based RR had a positive effect on the reading comprehension of the participants. The participants in the control group acquired a very small amount of comprehension ability through the treatment of the study while that in the experimental group revealed greater improvement in comprehension ability.

6.2. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

6.2.1. Limitations

One limitation that can hinder the researcher when carrying on the research is to employ some teachers that have been teaching the two classes of both groups. This can be difficult because they seem to be very busy teaching and may not be willing to grant their time for the interview. This is because they can refuse to join in the research. In addition, some teachers might not probably have a clear and accurate observations on 76 participants, and this will cause the intervention for both groups inaccurate.

The second possible limitation could be the offering of the permission of the school. This is one of the most common hardships when carrying on the research at the research site that was appropriate to the researcher before. The school where this research intended to be conducted could be not willing to spend quite much time for the methodology to be carried on. This is

because the research can partially influence to the class schedules as well as abit on the school curriculum. Also, a list of students for the treatment can be problematic when offering from the school offices.

It can be anticipated that the short time of implementation of the Repeated Reading treatment can produce less significant results as expected of improving reading comprehension. All participants employed in the methodology may become impatient to undertake the experimental weeks. Another deleterious side can be seen would be that both two groups of experimental design will feel the testing unhelpful because they assume that those will not involve in their learning course at school. The materials used in the treatment can take much time for the students to feel familiar. Because they may be familiar with the frame of the school curriculum and at this time they will take another course designed differently from their coursebook. This can definitely bear a burden for themselves when they understand nothing from the content as well as structures of the text which were extracted from the material.

One possible consideration is the feasibility of the intervention to be utilized during lessons within the classroom context. The time constraint is a factor appearing in language classrooms, time can be not enough to facilitate the reading process of each student, especially in a large experimental group of 76 students. Besides, one significant difficulty affecting to the results as well as accuracy of the research is the use of semi opened-ended interview for collecting quantitative data. This can be hard to control all participants to write down what they are asked to do, particularly in this research – advantages and disadvantages with the treatment. Although the study fulfilled the difficulties of learners studying reading comprehension through RR with audio, there were still some limitations listed after the study. This study was finished with 14 weeks, one week for pre-test, 12 weeks of the treatment and 1 week for post-test. This study can be considered to be relatively reliable because of its length of research.

The study was done at Vo Minh Duc high school with two classes at grade 10, which indicated that there was no relevant comparison with other high schools in Thu Dau Mot City. Therefore, it can be conducted whether the results still remain possibly stable if the study is carried out at other schools with the same treatment.

6.2.2. Future directions

Audio-based RR, as a strong tool, may assist all struggling readers by enhancing reading skills. Students' acquisition of new words has been aided with using audio-based RR in reading exercises. Learners became used to being more proficient learners as a result of the audio-based RR, which helped them to improve their reading skills. Because listening to an audio model is similar to reading a book, it can help students to improve their vocabulary, pronunciation, as well as understanding. Then, there is potential for further research to adapt audio into reading activities, especially RR with audio assistance. I believe that RR with audio will assist instructors in becoming more receptive to reading activities that would inspire EFL learners, as well as better equip teachers to deal with the problems of students from different high schools in Thu Dau Mot. Furthermore, the future researcher is suggested to choose participants in grade 11 and 12 to examine whether the effectiveness of audio-based RR would be equivalent with different grades. If there is some significant difference in the effect of RR strategy, this can be meaningful for the research in terms of using audio-based RR on three grades in high school educational system. Audio-based RR strategy can be useful to develop the reading comprehension of learners and also prepare EFL students well for the next grade.

6.3. RECOMMENDATIONS

One suggestion is to limit the length of every reading session and widen the intervention period into a duration. The word identification, deep acquisition of new words accumulated from Repeated Reading parts are still weak.

I realized that the effectiveness of audio-based RR was significantly successful. Nevertheless, time was quite a bit troublesome because teachers and I found that it was difficult to employ more time to instruct and engage participants in the treatment because some more advanced participants completed the lesson earlier those who were just less advanced. Therefore, I suggest that a consolidation part should be included in the treatment for those who had better performance. This can help maintain the atmosphere of the classroom and also keep time useful. Additionally, other less advanced participants will not be distracted by others when they are still under the treatment. This is one possible measure to prevent time constraints and other distractions in the class.

Another solution to control the quality of quantitative data collection from interview with semi opened-ended type is to employ some supporting other EFL learners.

One possible alternative to have teachers in the interview as well as receiving permission from the school is that the research can be carried on after their mid-term test on the first semester because this can lower some problems of influencing to scheduled plans of the semester.

6.3.1. Recommendations for teachers

This reading method is mostly used by instructors to improve their learners' fluency. Students whose reading is correct but choppy advantage from repeated reading because it helps them build automaticity, or the ability to comprehend swiftly and effectively. Better comprehension and overall reading performance are associated with automaticity. Therefore, teachers are suggested to apply audio-based RR into reading activities in the classroom.

6.3.2. Recommendations for students

The technique of having a learner read the same material again and over until their reading is fluent and error-free is known as repeated reading. Individually or in a group environment, this approach can be used in. Originally, repeated reading with audio was intended to help EFL learners with learning impairments who struggled with reading. Therefore, this technique will assist the majority of students.

6.4. IMPLICATIONS

Generally speaking, teachers always play an essential role in the improvement of learners' learning process. Therefore, teachers should accumulate more various teaching methodologies and also take advantage of other teaching aids. These will strongly facilitate teacher to have better performance and enhance knowledgeable and pedagogical skill as well.

Additionally, materials used in high schools should be added with some affective teaching methods, which facilitates teachers to arouse the classroom and also make students feel more excited in learning, especially reading skill. Besides, teachers are stimulated to set up special activities to help learners feel at ease with reading learning process. For example, the teacher can give their students more additional lessons or occasional activities to reinforce students' competence in learning process, particularly reading learning routine. Following this, students' demand of learning is different and diverse, therefore, teachers should understand their interest of learning to find out which teaching methods as well as strategies are suitable for them. Furthermore, teaching activities play an important part in developing students' competence because these activities can facilitate and create strong connections between teachers and students. Hence, students should understand the role of instructional strategies which help themselves improve their learning process. Even though the results from the study answered the research questions, there are also some recommendations that should be deliberated for further studies. First and foremost, the study was conducted within around 14 weeks to examine the effectiveness of audio-based RR to improve scores of reading section for grade 10 students.

APPENDIX/ APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Reading Test (Test A) – 20 minutes	
Name:	Class:
Proctor:	

THE MODERN CARS OF THE FUTURE

Today's cars are smaller, safer, cleaner, and more economical than their predecessors, but the car of the future will be far more pollution-free than those on the road today. Several new types of automobile engines have already been developed that run on alternative sources of power, such as electricity, compressed natural gas, methanol, steam, hydrogen, propane. Electricity, however, is the only zero-emission option presently available.

Although electric vehicles will not be truly practical until a powerful, **compact** battery or another dependable source of current is available, transportation experts foresee a new assortment of electric vehicles entering everyday life: shorter-range commuter electric cars, three-wheeled neighborhood cars, electric delivery vans, bikes, and trolleys.

As automakers work to develop practical electric vehicles, urban planners and utility engineers are focusing on infrastructure systems to support and make the best use of the new cars. Public **charging** facilities will need to be as common as today's gas stations. Public parking spots on the street or in commercial lots will need to be equipped with devices that allow drivers to charge their batteries while they stop, dine, or attend a concert. To encourage the use of electric vehicles, the most convenient parking in transportation centers might be reserved for electric cars.

Planners foresee electric shuttle buses, trains, and neighborhood vehicles all meeting at transit centers that would have facilities for charging and renting. **Commuters** will be able to rent a variety of electric cars to suit their needs: light trucks, one-person three-wheelers, small cars, or electric/gasoline **hybrid** cars for longer trips, which will no doubt take place on automated freeways capable of handling five times the number of vehicles that can be carried by a freeway today.

Question 1. The following electric vehicles are all mentioned in the passage EXCEPT:

- A. Trolleys
- B. Trains
- C. Vans
- D. planes

Question 2. The author's purpose in the passage is to

- A. criticize conventional vehicles
- B. describe the possibilities for transportation in the future
- C. narrate a story about alternative energy vehicles
- D. support the invention of electric cars

Question 3. The passage would most likely be followed by details about

- A. the neighborhood of the future
- B. pollution restrictions in the future
- C. automated freeways
- D. electric shuttle buses

Question 4. The word "**compact**" in the second paragraph is closest in meaning to

- A. long-range
- B. concentrated
- C. inexpensive
- D. squared

Question 5. In the second paragraph the author implies that

- A. everyday life will stay such the same in the future.
- B. a dependable source of electric energy will eventually be developed.
- C. a single electric vehicle will eventually replace several modern of transportation.
- D. electric vehicles are not practical for the future.

Question 6. According to the passage, public parking lots of the future will be more convenient than they are today

- A. as common as today's gas stations
- B. much large than they are today
- C. equipped with charging devices

Question 7. The word "charging" in this passage refer to

- A. parking
- B. credit cards
- C. electricity
- D. lightening

Question 8. It can be inferred from the passage that

- A. the present cars are more economical than their future generation
- B. electricity is the best alternative source of power as it is almost free of pollution
- C. the present electric engines are the best option as being practical
- D. many new types of practical electric engines have been developed

Question 9. he word "hybrid" in paragraph 4 is closest in meaning to

- A. automated
- B. hazardous
- C. futuristic
- D. combination

Question 10. The word "commuters" in paragraph 4 refer to

- A. cab drivers
- B. visitors
- C. daily travelers
- D. shoppers

ENDING

Answers

1-D	2-B	3-C	4-B	5-B
6-D	7-C	8-B	9-D	10-C

APPENDIX B

Reading Test (Test B) – 30 minutes	
Name:	Class:
Proctor:	

The advent of the Internet may be one of the most important technological developments in recent years. Never before have so many people had access to so many different sources of information. For all of the Internet's advantages, however, people are currently becoming aware of some of its drawbacks and are looking for creative solutions. Among the current problems, which include a general lack of reliability and numerous security concerns, the most crucial is speed.

First of all, the Internet has grown very quickly. In 1990, only a few academics had ever heard of the Internet. In 1996, over 50 million people used it. Every year, the number of people with access to the Internet doubles. The rapid growth has been a problem. The computer systems which run the Internet have not been able to keep up with the demand. Also, sometimes, a request for information must pass through many routing computers before the information can be **obtained**. A request for information made in Paris might have to go through computers in New York, Los Angeles and Tokyo in order to obtain the required information. Consequently, the service is often slow and unpredictable. Service also tends to be worse when the Internet is busiest - during the business day of the Western Hemisphere - which is also when companies need its service the most.

Some people are trying to **harness** the power of networked computers in such a way as to avoid this problem. In 1995, a group of American universities banded together to form what has come to be known as Internet

II. Internet II is a smaller, more specialized system intended for academic use. Since it is more specialized, fewer users are allowed access. Consequently, the time required to receive information has decreased.

Businesses are beginning to explore a possible **analogue** to the Internet II. Many businesses are creating their own "Intranets". These are systems that can only be used by the members of the same company. In theory, fewer users should translate into a faster system. Intranets are very useful for large national and international companies whose branches need to share information. Another benefit of an Intranet is an increased amount of security. Since only company employees have access to the information on the Intranet, **their** information is protected from competitors. While there is little doubt that the Internet will eventually be a fast and reliable service, industry and the academic community have taken their own steps toward making more practical global networks.

Question 1. According to the passage, which of the following is not true of the Internet ?

- A. It tends to be unreliable.
- B. It has created a sense of financial security.
- C. It is too expensive to access.
- D. It has become increasingly less popular.

Question 2. According to the passage, which of the following statements was true in 1990?

- A. The Internet was a secure means to gain information.
- B. The Internet experienced enormous growth rates.
- C. Internet data proved to be impractical.
- D. Few people were using the Internet.

Question 3. According to the author, what is one reason why the Internet is sometimes slow?

- A. Phone lines are often too busy with phone calls and fax transmissions to handle Internet traffic.
- B. Most people do not have computers that are fast enough to take advantage of the Internet.

- C. Often a request must travel through many computers before it reaches its final destination.
- D. Scientists take up too much time on the Internet, thus slowing it down for everyone else.

Question 4. The word “**obtained**” in line 10 is closest in meaning to_.

- A. Understood
- B. Acquired
- C. Purchased
- D. distributed

Question 5. The word “**harness**” in line 15 is closest in meaning to__.

- A. utilize
- B. disguise
- C. steal
- D. block

Question 6. According to the passage, what benefits does Internet II have over the Internet I?

- A. There is no governmental intervention regulating Internet II.
- B. Small businesses pay higher premiums to access to the Internet.
- C. Internet II contains more information than the Internet.
- D. Internet II has fewer users and therefore is faster to access.

Question 7. The word “**analogue**” in line 20 most nearly means_____.

- A. Similarity
- B. alternative
- C. use
- D. solution

Question 8. The word “**their**” in line 25 refers to_.

- A. competitors
- B. company employees
- C. Intranets
- D. companies

Question 9. With which of the following conclusions would the author probably agree?

- A. Fewer academic communities need to create their own Internet systems.
- B. Companies who develop their own Intranets are limiting their information data base.
- C. The technology used by Internet creators is too complex for computer owners to understand.
- D. An Internet system with fewer users would be quicker.

Question 10. All of the following are advantages of business “ Intranets” mentioned in the passage EXCEPT _____

- A. they provide a higher level of security.
- B. they share information with other company branches.
- C. they are cheaper than other alternatives.
- D. they move data faster.

ENDING

Answers

1-D	2-D	3-C	4-B	5-A
6-D	7-A	8-B	9-B	10-C

APPENDIX C

Questionnaire Survey

No. of Statement	Participant's name:				
	Likert Scale				
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1. I was engaged more effectively in reading materials with audio-based RR than silent reading.					
2. I was able to assess the meaning of unknown words more relatively accurately thanks to audio-based RR.					
3. The treatment increased not only reading comprehension but also listening skill as well.					
4. The treatment not only improved accurate pronunciation but also increased reading fluency.					
5. The treatment facilitated me to do reading tasks more quickly than silent reading.					
6. The treatment provided me a multimodal reading experience, which helped me avoid frustration in reading.					
7. RR gave me a substantial improvement on word identification as well as decoding skills by giving a variety of exposures to similar words.					
8. The treatment helped me read phrases that were longer, including more syntactic and syntactic and phonetic units.					
9. The treatment taught me to guess the meaning of unknown words or phrases with ambiguous grammatical points.					
10. The treatment raised learner autonomy more effectively.					

APPENDIX D

Semi Opened-ended Interview Sheet

No. of questions	Participant’s name:	Answers
	Time:	
	Questions asked	
1	What are the disadvantages did you have in the first week of treatment?	
2	What are the advantages did you have in the first week?	
3	In which weeks did you find the treatment beneficial?	
4	In which weeks did you find the treatment difficult to be with?	

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